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RECONSTRUCTION OF DEFECTS AND DEFORMATIONS OF THE ZYGOMATICO-ORBITAL COMPLEX USING INDIVIDUALIZED IMPLANTS

Husanov D.R., Shomurodov K.E., Musaev Sh.Sh.

Department of Maxillofacial Surgery, Tashkent State Dental Institute, Uzbekistan

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Relevance. According to a number of authors, injuries of the middle zone of the face account for 18-31% of injuries of the facial bones, and among them injuries of the zygomatic-orbital complex (SOC) up to 70% are more common. However, the use of traditional methods of treatment for this pathology does not give the desired effect.

Purpose of the study. Improving the effectiveness of treatment through the use of individualized bone cement implants in reconstructive surgery in patients with defects and deformities of the zygomatic-orbital complex.

Material and methods. In the clinic of the Tashkent State Dental Institute for the period from 2019 to 2022, reconstructive surgeries were performed with the installation of individualized 3D implants based on polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA) for defects and deformities of the mucosal system. At the stage of treatment, patients underwent computed tomography (CT), with mandatory processing of CT scans in the bone mode, the slice thickness was not more than 1.0 mm. The obtained data of patients were recorded on an electronic medium and transferred to the manufacturer of the 3D implant.

Research results. When developing a technique for manufacturing individual implants from PMMA using 3D printing, experimental samples of individual (based on CT data) endoprostheses for the reconstruction of the OCS were obtained. The created implants exactly repeat the shape and contours of the facial part of the skull, have all the strength characteristics (corresponding to the bone tissue). The designed endoprostheses are fixed with standard mini-screws to the bone edges of the defect. An original technology of a personalized approach to the replacement of postoperative defects in the maxillofacial region with implants from.

Summarizing all the above, we can conclude that the new complex technique we have developed for preoperative planning and the creation of individual implants from PMMA for the reconstruction of the OCS is clinically applicable and in demand in modern areas of reconstructive surgery. Performing reconstructive surgeries using PMMA implants will allow achieving high functional and cosmetic results, as well as improving the quality of life of patients with defects and deformities of the OC.

Conclusions. In modern reconstructive surgery, research is aimed at developing an individual technology for endoprosthesis replacement of the facial part of the skull. This direction is facilitated by the rapid development of 3D technologies and 3D

printing. To date, techniques for the manufacture of individual titanium implants using a 3D printer are already known. However, their implementation is associated with a number of complications inherent in metal prostheses (inflammation, instability in the area of contact with bone tissue, eruption through soft tissues, etc.). In our study, we have developed a fundamentally new technique for obtaining geometrically complex implants based on PMMA for the reconstruction of the OCS using 3D technologies. PMMA implant material meets all the requirements for medical materials used in reconstructive surgery. The developed technique for creating individual implants from PMMA makes it possible to compensate for complex defects in the maxillofacial region. Further clinical study of the developed technique for the reconstruction of the SOC will allow solving the complex problems of social isolation and functional inferiority of patients.